

TAXING THE INFORMAL SECTOR

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Abstract: This paper examines the literature on informal economy taxation, highlighting current developments, assessing important arguments and proposing different solutions. The limited revenue potential, high collection costs, and potential negative effects on small businesses have always been the main points of contention in the taxation issue. The more indirect advantages of informal taxes in terms of economic growth, general tax compliance, and governance have been emphasized more and more in recent debates. More studies are required to examine the costs and advantages for everyone involved, including quasi-voluntary compliance, administrative and political incentives for change, and citizen-state negotiations over taxes.

Keywords: informal sector, shadow economy, method, tax base, unified system, approach, tax credit.

НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЕ НЕФОРМАЛЬНОГО СЕКТОРА

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Главный специалист отдела развития государственно-частного партнерства, разработки, координации и анализа проектов в области энергетики и инфраструктуры

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается литература по налогообложению неформальной экономики, выделяя текущие тенденции, оценивая важные аргументы и предлагая различные решения. Ограниченный потенциал доходов, высокие затраты на сбор налогов и возможные негативные последствия для малого бизнеса всегда были основными спорными моментами в вопросах налогообложения. В последнее время в дискуссиях все больше подчеркиваются косвенные

преимущества неформальных налогов с точки зрения экономического роста, общей налоговой дисциплины и управления. Требуются дополнительные исследования для изучения затрат и выгод для всех заинтересованных сторон, включая квазидобровольное соблюдение, административные и политические стимулы к изменениям, а также переговоры между гражданами и государством по налоговым вопросам.

Ключевые слова: неформальный сектор, теневой рынок, метод, налоговая база, унифицированная система, подход, налоговый кредит.

NOFORMAL SEKTORNI SOLIQQA TORTISH

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Energetika va infratuzilma loyihalarini rivojlantirish, muvofiqlashtirish va tahlil qilish bo'limining davlat-xususiy sheriklikni rivojlantirish bo'yicha bosh mutaxassisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada noformal iqtisodiyotni soliqqa tortish bo'yicha adabiyotlar ko'rib chiqilgan bo'lib, unda hozirgi tendensiyalar tahlil qilingan, muhim dalillar baholangan va turli yechimlar taklif etilgan. Cheklangan daromad salohiyati, soliqlar yig'imining yuqori xarajatlari hamda kichik biznesga mumkin bo'lgan salbiy ta'sir har doim soliqqa tortish masalalaridagi asosiy bahsli jihatlar bo'lib kelgan. So'nggi munozaralarda iqtisodiy o'sish, umumiy soliq intizomi va boshqaruv nuqtai nazaridan noformal soliqlarning bilvosita afzalliklari tobora ko'proq ta'kidlanmoqda. Fuqarolar va davlat o'rtasidagi soliqlar bo'yicha muzokaralar, kvasidobrovoliy rioya qilish, o'zgarishlar uchun ma'muriy va siyosiy rag'batlarni o'rganish uchun qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar talab etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: noformal sektor, soya iqtisodiyoti, metod, soliq bazasi, yagona tizim, yondashuv, soliq imtiyozi.

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Introduction. The term “informal sector” tends to be contentious. Joshi et.al (2014) cites definition from Peattie (1987) who argues that the concept tends to be vague due to serving the interests and needs of a variety of different groups. Another definition from Keith Hart (1973) is cited by

Joshi et.al (2014) who originally defined “informal sector” as employment that is not a part of formal labor markets. Although these definitions are partly related to informal sector in Uzbekistan, they do not encompass the complete definition of what the government of Uzbekistan think of informal sector. However, Joshi et.al (2014) also cites International Labor Organization that used the term “informal sector” as small and micro businesses that circumvent taxation and are not affected by government regulation. This definition realistically describes the informal sector economy in Uzbekistan.

In 2019, January 17th Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on the state program for implementing the strategy of action in five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the year of active investments and social development”¹⁰⁰ was approved and this important document paved the way for reforming the informal sector in Uzbekistan. This document clearly outlines how the informal sector will be reduced by identifying methods of dealing with informal sector in a normative-legal document and also identifies which government organizations are responsible for ensuring timely and quality implementation of this reform. This paper is going to first propose a number of methods Uzbekistan has been using in an effort to deal with informal sector and then identify some of the methods of taxation of the informal sector proposed by Joshi et.al, and finally propose what policy options are the best way of taxing the informal sector in Uzbekistan.

The document above as a way of taxing informal sector has proposed taking the following measures in Uzbekistan:

The electronic system of formation of data on imported goods will be established.¹⁰¹ The reform policy agenda includes establishing data on imported goods electronically. Uzbekistan has been grappling with taxing informal sector due to problems related to gathering accurate data on imported goods. Introduction of a unified system of identification marking for certain goods and creation of an electronic database of product accounting by tax authorities is also extremely important step in establishing tax base and reduce informal sector.¹⁰² Also, legalizing and controlling e-commerce

¹⁰⁰ <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/4168757>

¹⁰¹ <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/4168757>

¹⁰² <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4168749?query=xufyona%20iqtisodiyot#sr-1>

has been proposed as a way of taxing informally conducted electronic transactions.

Another method proposed in the document is to tax informal sector in the housing and automobile market that account for the largest informal sector transactions. The housing market is by far the largest market in Uzbekistan where real estate agents and buyers are engaged in large-scale transactions and pay little tax to the government. Similarly, automobile market is responsible for the largest share of informal sector that the government receives little tax revenue. In order to deal with these informal sectors, the government of Uzbekistan is implementing a policy change that imposes tax on these large-scale transactions. So, the mechanism the government is planning to employ is as follows: when someone purchases a house or apartment, they used to have it notarized to gain legal ownership right over this property without showing any confirmation of tax payment receipt to the government at a notary office. But, now, the government is proposing to pass a legislation that will prevent notary offices from notarizing property rights of buyers unless proof of tax payment receipt is demonstrated. Similarly, the same mechanism is being used for automobile transactions.

Majority of the people in the informal sector who buy and sell houses — called “landlords” by local people — are informally unregistered street traders¹⁰³. These “landlords” marked their own territories in different communities of different cities in the country and local people living in these communities personally know these “landlords”. If local people want to sell their houses, they contact these “landlords” who help them sell their houses and, in return, “landlords” charge homeowners a fee, usually up to 5-7% of selling price of the houses for their service of matching buyers and also demand certain amount of remuneration from buyers. Similar arrangements work for automobile market too. The root cause of not moving to formal sector in these housing and automobile markets seems to be red tape, bureaucracy and harassment of businesses by some tax authorities that were severely criticized by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for making unannounced visits to small and micro businesses and imposing fines

¹⁰³ Author's own observations. No data is available on this.

on businesses for hiring workers informally who were paid cash wages or for accepting cash payments and not providing sales receipts for services and goods that they sell. Joshi et.al (2014) raises this concern in their paper which argues that formalization increases visibility of firms to state authorities, which may expose it to unfair treatment and harassment. With the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a new policy was introduced that forbade tax authorities from carrying out raids on businesses, and required them to obtain permission from the administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to order to carry out tax audit and tax inspection on businesses¹⁰⁴. This policy change had a positive impact on businesses that had been previously intimidated by some tax authorities that also caused some formal sector firms to move to informal sector to hide from arbitrary tax inspection raids carried out in a haphazard manner. The fact that firms that had previously paid taxes ceased paying taxes, in turn, had ripple effect on other formal sector firms that started evading taxes as well because of low tax morale. This situation is supported by empirical evidence provided by Weck (1983) who conducted an empirical analysis that exhibited a negative relationship between tax morale and informal sector. This is further supported by a more recent investigation by Torgler (2003) who conducted a multivariate analysis that demonstrated a negative relationship between tax morale and tax evasion. The policy change led many informal sector firms to formalizing because they were no longer subject to arbitrary and indiscriminate inspection by those tax authorities¹⁰⁵ and also motivated formal sector firms not to evade taxes because they were under the protection of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Moreover, the government has also begun to establish call-centers¹⁰⁶ in order to reduce informal sector or – “shadow” economy as specified in the document. The mechanism of using call-centers in an effort to deal with informal sector economy is as follows: social media, TVs and other plat-

¹⁰⁴ https://www.norma.uz/oz/qonunchilikda_yangi/soliq_tekshiruvlari_qanday_utkaziladi

¹⁰⁵ I would like to emphasize here that new leadership in Uzbekistan had a huge positive spillover effect on formalizing informal sector firms. Uzbekistan is very lucky to have Shavkat Mirziyoyev, our second President, who made many positive reforms that people of Uzbekistan enjoyed and benefited, particularly businesses and firms are much freer and less subject to government intervention that have encouraged and incentivized firms in the informal sector to formalize in Uzbekistan because businesses and firms are now protected by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

¹⁰⁶ <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4168749?query=xufyona%20iqqtisodiyot#sr-1>

forms have raised awareness about the importance of demanding sales receipts for goods and services people consume from sellers or suppliers (restaurants, shops and firms) and whenever people get their receipts from sellers or suppliers, 1% of total amount of payment for goods and services will be returned to buyers or consumers as a cashback. Whenever suppliers or sellers of goods and services refuse to give receipts for purchases, people (buyers or consumers) can report about this by using the call-center. The call-center also rewards those who blow the whistle and report to them about a business that is not providing sales receipts¹⁰⁷ for goods and services. This has led to an enormous reduction in informal sector activity in Uzbekistan because businesses and firms that only accept cash and therefore pay no income tax to the government are caught and fined, and firms and businesses that are not formally registered are unable to function because of not being able to generate sales receipts and are therefore forced to formalize. These methods have been used in Uzbekistan in order to “fight” against informal sector economy.

Joshi et.al (2014) proposed a number of policy options for taxing the informal sector that could be applicable to Uzbekistan. One possible approach proposed by Joshi et.al (2014, p.1332) is to tax informal sector indirectly by means of value-added tax (VAT). Joshi et.al (1332) argue that “the most important source of indirect tax revenue in most developing countries is VAT, with recent decades witnessing a broad shift from import tariffs to VAT, based largely on the premise that VAT is less economically distorting”. High administrative and compliance costs relative to revenue collected, they claim, are the main arguments why it would make more sense to tax the informal sector indirectly with value-added tax (VAT). According to Joshi et.al (2014), this method works by indirectly taxing the informal sector by taxing its inputs and refusing to give credit for tax on its inputs and sales.

Another commonly used tool in developing countries proposed by Joshi et.al (2014) is to use withholding taxes that is similar to indirect taxation. Joshi et.al (p.1333) argue that only tax complying businesses can use withholding taxes as a credit against their tax burden, which incentivizes

¹⁰⁷ When sales receipts are given to buyers, then the tax authorities can track the amount of business income that will be taxed.

non-compliant businesses to comply with tax laws. However, Keen (2007) casts doubt on the refundability of these withheld tax payments to compliant taxpayers in practice, claiming that “the limited administrative capacity in many developing countries suggests, however, that the implementation of the crediting arrangements is often imperfect” although he acknowledges that withholding taxes can be very efficient as they impose no extra charge on taxpayers in the formal sector. Despite this limited administrative capacity, Joshi et.al (2014) claim that withholding taxes, which are imposed by governments or larger companies on transactions involving small enterprises that might not be tax compliant, are very popular in developing countries and, in certain cases, account for a sizable portion of all revenue collected.

Joshi et.al (2014) proposes broadening the scope of common formal sector taxes through improved enforcement and compliance as an alternative to indirectly taxing businesses. Joshi et.al (p.1332) claim that reduced rates or rewards could be offered to small firms keeping effective records as additional incentives to encourage compliance. However, in addition to incentivizing small firms to remain small, both of these measures, they claim, may cause the tax system to become more complex. According to Joshi et.al (2014), although extremely high administrative costs of expanding formal sector taxes for the government may lead to harassment and abuse in the case of very small firms, for larger firms in the informal sector this method is likely to be appropriate.

Joshi et.al (2014) also suggest reduced costs and red tape involved in formalization as a way of dealing with informal sector. Joshi et.al (p.1334) claim that if firms that carry out cost and benefit analysis see that advantages of formalization are greater than the disadvantages, they may consider shifting to formal sector and they also clearly state that the benefits of formalization are “access to credit and capital markets, government procurement contracts, other external markets, and state-provided services and facilities” while “the cost of registration or getting licenses, the cost of tax compliance, and the cost of following labor laws and other regulations” may be incorporated into costs. Addressing these more general formalization costs and benefits, they claim, may be necessary to incentivize businesses to join the tax system.

Finally, Joshi et.al (2014) also propose one of the most popular approaches to taxing small firms in the informal sector. Joshi et.al (p.1333) suggest “presumptive taxes” – as defined¹⁰⁸, in simple terms, as tax on easily observable indicators that are correlated with the base we would ideally like to tax— as a way of taxing small firms in the informal sector. Loeprick (2009) argue that high compliance costs for small taxpayers and high costs of collection for tax administrations are two major impediments to taxing small informal sector firms and the use of presumptive tax can overcome these issues by making it easier for businesses to retain records and for tax collectors to estimate tax liabilities by employing a simplified indicator of the tax base. Joshi et.al (2014) cite an argument from Loeprick (2009) who stresses turnover tax as the tax base as opposed to Sadka and Tanzi (1993) who argue that a tax on gross assets should be used. Joshi et.al (2014) also argue that non-financial indicators such as floor area or number of employees could be used in order to estimate tax liabilities. This is very similar to proxy-means test that means collecting data on easily observable indicators, and using those to predict the value of tax base¹⁰⁹.

However, Joshi et.al (2014, p.1333) cautions that a significant trade-off exists between equity and simplicity when selecting presumptive systems. Adopting a tax base that is considerably easier to detect and monitor is the driving force behind the presumptive system, which lowers the firm's compliance burden. However, Bird&Wallace (2003, p.21) argue that the risks of horizontal inequality and the risks of incentivizing businesses to remain in the presumptive tax regime rather than graduate increase with the gap between the presumptive tax base and the generally applicable tax base.

To sum up, taxing informal sector firms may lead to improved tax morale and a culture of tax compliance in Uzbekistan, potentially leading to significant benefits in terms of long-term revenue collection, economic growth, and the quality of governance. Which policy options would be the best way to achieve these goals are hard to tell precisely, although taxing the informal sector using indirect methods, particularly VAT, seems to be

¹⁰⁸ This definition was provided on a video lesson prepared by Professor Jon M. Bakija based on Joshi et.al (2014) for Center for Development Economics, Williams College in 2024.

¹⁰⁹ This definition was provided on a video lesson prepared by Professor Jon M. Bakija for Center for Development Economics, Williams College in 2024.

better as value-added tax (VAT) would cause less economic distortion and would also incentivize informal sector firms engaged with formal sector firms to formalize so as to claim tax credits. By contrast, taxing the informal sector directly would not be recommended in case of Uzbekistan as it would involve extremely high administrative and compliance costs relative to the revenue collected. However, although indirect methods of informal sector taxation seem to be better policy options for Uzbekistan in general, in some specific cases such as small restaurants and small shops, presumptive tax could be more effective in terms of revenue collection. This situation shows that a mix of different policy options could also be optimal and worth considering costs and benefits.

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